

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan)

Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan: Lexical relationship in some animal and plant terms

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Abstract: This study examines the results of a geolinguistic approach to the Sino-Tibetan family by combining data described separately for Sinitic and Tibeto-Burman in the projects *Studies of Asian Geolinguistics* and *Studies of Asian and African Geolinguistics*. Four animal and plant terms were discussed: ‘dog’, ‘pig’, ‘rice plant’, and ‘wheat’. Among them, ‘dog’ and ‘rice’ exhibit a lexical relationship at the root level, whereas ‘pig’ shows different roots in the two language groups, and ‘wheat’ exhibits their loan relationship.*

Keywords: Sino-Tibetan; geolinguistics; lexical distribution; language contact; morphological difference

1. Introduction

In light of recent research, Sinitic and Tibeto-Burman are considered distinct branches of the Sino-Tibetan single-language family. However, the ILCAA projects *Studies of Asian Geolinguistics* and *Studies of Asian and African Geolinguistics* have treated both as separate members owing to differences in history, research focus, data availability, quantity, and geographical density. This study examines the results of combining data from both language groups.

Recent studies (M. Zhang et al. 2019, Sagart et al. 2019, H. Zhang et al. 2020) have shown that Sinitic and Tibeto-Burman are closely related (Sino-Tibetan), with Sinitic

SUZUKI, Hiroyuki, Kenji YAGI, and Fumiki SUZUKI. 2023. Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan: Lexical relationship in some animal and plant terms. *Studies in Geolinguistics* 3: 164–179. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8437113>

* An earlier version of the article was presented at the workshop entitled ‘Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan and beyond’ in the 55th International conference of Sino-Tibetan Languages and Linguistics. We should thank the participants who provided us with insightful comments. The work was supported by the ILCAA Joint Research Project ‘Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics’ and JSPS KAKENHI Grant Numbers JP17H04774, JP18H00670, JP18H05219, JP19K13187, JP20K13032, JP23H00625, and JP23K00486.

being the first branch of Sino-Tibetan (Bradley 2022).¹ An essay combining Sinitic and Tibeto-Burman using the geolinguistic method (see Shirai, this volume) is possible because the dataset is readily available.

From a technical viewpoint, combining Sinitic and Tibeto-Burman data is not complicated. However, we should pay attention to the choice of the word form. A target may share an innovation to signal a lexical derivational relationship, unlike a combination of the datasets consisting of different language families (Ebihara and Saitô, this volume).

A newly acquired term cannot adequately explain the Sino-Tibetan relationship. For instance, the word forms for ‘horse’ are common in most Sino-Tibetan languages (Figure 1)²; however, the introduction of the ‘horse’ is assumed to be after 3500 Before Common Era (BCE), a period that is considered to be the domestication of horses in Central Asia (see Librado et al. 2021). Furthermore, the word form for ‘horse’ is regarded as a *Wanderwort* ‘migratory word’ that is attested across language families (Bjørn 2022).

In addition to the ‘horse’ shown in Figure 1, this article considers four lexical forms, the ‘dog,’ ‘pig,’ ‘rice plant,’ and ‘wheat.’ We present maps containing both Sinitic and Tibetan-Burman data simultaneously. This study aims to demonstrate how Sino-Tibetan linguistic maps function in geolinguistic studies. The abbreviations SN (Sinitic), TB (Tibeto-Burman), and ST (Sino-Tibetan) are used in the tables and legends. The symbols on the maps are red for SN and brown for TB. For detailed descriptions and analyses of each SN and TB lexical item, please refer to Table 1. For bibliographical information on the data sources, see LAA (2021) and LAAA-III (2023).

Table 1 Previous works of each lexical item.

SN	‘horse’	Yagi (2022a)
	‘dog’	Yagi (2022b)
	‘rice plant’	Yagi and Ueya (2021)
	‘wheat’	F. Suzuki (2023)
TB	‘horse’	Ebihara et al. (2022a)
	‘dog’	Ebihara et al. (2022b)
	‘pig’	H. Suzuki (2019)
	‘rice plant’	H. Suzuki et al. (2016, 2021)
	‘wheat’	H. Suzuki et al. (2023a)

¹ We find more recent studies examining the Sino-Tibetan lexical relationship, for example, Jacques and d’Alpoim-Guedes (2023) for ‘*Zanthoxylum*’.

² A clear exception is observed in Tibetic and Tamangic languages, which use a word derived from Type B: **r-ta*. In many Tibetic languages, a form derived from Type A (**s-mraj*) is used for a word meaning ‘wild yak’ (Literary Tibetan [LT] ‘*brong*’).

- SN:
- A. type
 - A-1 马 ma
 - ⊕ A-2 马儿 mar
 - A. **s/m-raŋ* type
 nbzəŋ, m̥zəŋ³¹, ^abrā, wə, lu, ran, zɯ, ɬəq, 'jy, kɔ̃, guē¹³, buro, byin, nyang, m̥ɰ³⁵, man, myin^H, sɔ̃rɔ, mbo ro, mbro, vre, fire, etc.; mo²¹ku⁵⁵lu⁵⁵, mu²¹pa⁵⁵, mɔ²¹pha²¹, mo⁴⁴ŋ²¹, mjo⁴⁴tha⁴², etc. (suffixed); a⁵⁵ŋ(ŋ)²¹, a²¹bəŋ²¹, a⁵⁵mo³¹, i³⁵mv⁵³, g̃um³¹raŋ³¹, gim rang, pa³¹xoŋ³⁵ (prefixed); a⁵⁵mo³¹za³¹, etc. (affixed).
 - ✓ B. **r-ta* type
 ɭta, rta, ʂta, ta, ^hta, ^hto, te⁵³, da¹, etc.
 - ▲ A-3 马子 ma tθɿ
 - △ A-4 马特 ma ku
 - C. **ghoḍā* type
 (N)gohḍa:q, guree, gura, gum⁴raŋ¹, k̃ierü, keru, kuri, kor g̃u-ri, etc; sə-kuu, etc. (prefixed).
 ⊕ C-compound type
 sya-n +C: sa gol, sa kawr, sa-koi, sāl kòl, si-kwe.
 - △ D. **k-sreʔ* type
 kǎ θe³, kǎ¹¹se⁴⁵, se³¹, θè, ngshe, etc.
 - ✓ X. others
 lalo, cop̃i, s^həp̃ü² mok, pferi, ^hgɔ̃, etc.
- TB:

Fig. 1 'Horse' in Sino-Tibetan.

2. ‘Dog’

Figures 2 and 3 show the word forms for ‘dog’ in ST. SN and TB employ common roots of a word for ‘dog’ (Type A in SN and TB).

- A.
 ☆ A-1 犬k^heiŋ
 B.
 ○ B-1 狗kou, kɿ, kau, kai, ki, tɛiv, teicɯ
 ● B-2 狗儿kəu ər, 狗儿kəur
 □ B-3 狗子kou tsɿ, ke tsæʔ, kieu tsɿ, kau a, e tsie
 C.
 ☆ C Others: 来福, 地羊ti iəŋ
 □ B-4 狗娃子kəu va tsəʔ
 △ B-5 狗团kəu (k-)jiaN
 SN:
 — A. *d-*kw*-*ay*-*n* type
 c^hi⁵³, ci⁵⁵, tɛ^hə, khur³³, tshi³³, tshz¹¹khv³³,
 k^hi³³, khui⁴⁴, phur⁵³, kui³¹, tefü, kei, si, ʔüy,
 ci, güy, thwī, hi, thi¹¹, ²³dži, šəy, hui, i, üi,
 ʃi³³, fū za, thwi, wī, gui hen, ʔüy, foi, hi,
 etc.; tɛhəru, chi⁵⁵bo⁵⁵, khur³¹ga³¹,
 khur³³jo³³, khli-tsa, khi:bu, fhurro, khira,
 khinu, etc. (suffixed); ɔ³¹khur³¹, azü,
 mɔ⁵⁵khur²¹, etsü, lə³¹kha³⁵, ³jukyu, əgi³¹,
 atsü, etc. (prefixed)
 TB:
 ◀ A+C: khe³³ne⁵⁵, khəna, khue⁵³ɿ³³
 △ C+A: 'no kju, nā ki
 / B. **m-par* ɤ*pra* type
 phur³, phv³, phi³, etc.
 ○ C. **na* type
 nagi, nā ki, 'nakyn, etc. (suffixed); a³³no²¹,
 etc. (prefixed)
 □ D. *hapa* type
 haba, xapa, hapa, etc.
 ∨ X. Others
 wathi, kots^ho, a-chak, wək, boh, nyi⁴mtur:²,
 tsuʔyu, etc.

Fig. 2 ‘Dog’ in Sino-Tibetan.

Fig. 3 ‘Dog’ in Sino-Tibetan (ST borderland enlarged).

The SN *quan* 犬 (OC *[k]^{wh}[e][n]?) and TB *d-k^wəy-n are from the same root. Most SN languages and varieties use *gou* 狗 (OC *Cə.k^hro?) for ‘dog’, considered to have originally been borrowed from Hmong-Mien (Akitani et al. 2022).³ In addition, the TB languages spoken in south-western Yunnan use other roots.

Tibetic languages spoken in north-eastern Tibetosphere (mainly Amdo Tibetan) distinguish a large herding dog (< *d-k^wəy-n) from a small long-haired pet dog by borrowing the Sinitic form *habagou* 哈巴狗 ‘Pekinese’ (Ebihara et al. 2022b). Sound forms of the same origin in the SN and TB generally follow their proto-forms (proto-Sinitic and proto-TB). For example, Tibetic follows the sound correspondence of each variety with LT *khyi* (or its ancient variant *k̄yi*). The present dataset suggests that there is no influence beyond these branches.

³ However, this view is still in debates.

3. ‘Pig’

Figures 4 and 5 show the word forms for ‘pig’ (general term) in ST.

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| <p>A. <i>zhu</i> 猪 type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A-1 <i>zhu</i> 猪: tʂu, tʂy, tʂɿ, tsu, tsy, tsɿ, tsy, tsɿ, tey, tei, teie, ʃy, ʃy, ʃi; pʃu, ty, ti, tu, tuu, te, tiu, tiəu, tɔy, ʔdu, ly, li, etc. ⊖ A-2 <i>zhur</i> 猪儿: tʂur, tsur, tʂyər, ʃy zɿ, tsu ə, tsu v, tsuβ əl, tsy ər, tsu ə, tsu ai, tsəf ər, tsy zɿʔ, tʂuəv, etc. ⊕ A-3 <i>zhuzi</i> 猪子: tʂu tsɿ, tsu tsɿ, tsu ve, tɔy tə, tsu tsəʔ, tsu ləʔ, etc. ⊗ A-4 <i>zhuli</i> 猪哩: tsu ɛ, tɔy lei, ʃy li ⊗ A-5 <i>zhunong</i> 猪农: tsɿ nonɿ <p>SN</p> <p>／ A. PTB *pʷak: pʰaʔ, haʃ, va, vɛ, paʃ, weʔ, etc.</p> <p>◆ B. Proto-Tani *rjek: ʔa' re.</p> <p>TB</p> <p>○ C. archaic loan from Sinitic <i>zhu</i> 猪: te, etc.</p> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊕ A-6-1 <i>zhulo</i> 猪罗: tsɿ lu, tsy ləu, tsy lo ⊗ A-6-2 <i>zhulolo</i> 猪唠唠: tʂu lə lə, tʂu lao lao, tsy loo loo, tɔy lo lo, tsu lə lə, etc. <p>B. <i>xi</i> 豨 type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> △ kʰy, kʰyi, kʰye, kʰə, kʰui, kʰəu, hui, etc. <p>C. <i>lolo</i> type: onomatopoeia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ C-1 <i>lolo</i> 唠唠: lə lə, lau lau, no no, etc. ◻ C-2 <i>heilolo</i> 黑唠唠: xei lə lə <p>D. others: Muslim avoid “pig” as taboo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☆ D-1 <i>heizi</i> 黑子 ☆ D-2 <i>jiudiwen</i> 就地闻 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D. derived from Sinitic <i>zhu</i> 猪: tʂu. □ E. <i>IV</i>-type: lə lə, bi la, etc. * X. others |
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Fig. 4 ‘Pig’ in Sino-Tibetan.

Fig. 5 'Pig' in Sino-Tibetan (ST borderland enlarged).

Although pigs are widely domesticated in the ST area,⁴ Figure 4 shows that SN and TB employ different roots of the word for the 'pig'. The root of SN is derived from *zhu* 猪 (OC *tra > MC trjo) with a minority derived from *xī* 豨 (OC *q^həjʔ > MC xj+jX), whereas the principal root of TB is derived from *p^wak (STEDT #1006; Type A) with

⁴ The first domestication of pigs in China dates back to ca. 6000 BCE (Price and Hongo 2020). This period is before the hypothetical split of SN and TB.

two minorities; one is derived from *rjek (STEDT #6019; Type B), whereas the other is a form including a denti-alveolar plosive or affricate initial (Type C).⁵

SN *zhu* was most likely the original connection for type C TB. The distribution of Type C, which is limited to the Baic (Bai) and Bisic (Tujia) languages, is closely connected to Sinitic languages from the viewpoint of language contact. SN Type C and some subtypes of Type A contain a /IV/ syllable, which can be explained as an onomatopoeia for calling pigs (e.g., Shen 2005:165). Interestingly, some TB languages use a similar form (Type E), including examples with the initial /l/ in the word form, some of which are connected to an expressive reflecting the addressing pigs, although no reports have identified the lexical origin. However, it is possible that the /IV/ syllable also functions in addressing pigs.⁶ Nevertheless, this commonality is coincidental from a geolinguistic viewpoint.

New word forms that avoid taboos in Muslim culture were also found in SN (Type D). Several TB languages are also spoken in similar cultural environments, such as in Qinghai and Gansu; however, it has not been reported whether the word ‘pig’ was substituted by another form. Notably, Type D-1 uses the morpheme ‘black’ for ‘pig’, which is generally black in the given region. Some Tibetic languages have a similar implication to the word derived from *phag*, which is always black (H. Suzuki 2019).

4. ‘Rice plant’

SN and TB have many roots for the rice-related semantic field, such as ‘rice plant’, ‘rice grain’, and ‘cooked rice’; for details on TB, see Suzuki et al. (2016). Figures 6 and 7 show the word forms for ‘rice plant’ in ST.

It is believed that rice cultivation originated within the current Sinitic-speaking area (Huang et al. 2012). Hence, the rice plant has played an essential role in the alimentionation of the people inhabiting the ST-speaking area. As mentioned previously, many ST languages possess multiple lexical roots for rice-related words. Due to this background, word forms for ‘rice plant’ in the languages within ST diverged greatly. This led to difficulty in identifying cognates between the SN and TB.

The root of SN is derived from *dao* 稻, whereas the root of TB is derived from various forms, such as *b-ras (STEDT #2071), *khrəy (STEDT #5867), and *ma-y 𑄎 *mey (STEDT #2445). The last root is related to SN *mi* 米 ‘rice grain’; *khrəy is used for ‘millet’ in some TB languages (H. Suzuki et al. 2023b, c).

⁵ Note that large lexical discrepancies are attested in specific terms for ‘pig’, such as ‘boar’, ‘sow’, and ‘piglet’, especially in the eastern Tibetosphere (H. Suzuki 2022).

⁶ In the Tibetic context, the /IV/ syllable is connected to a noun for ‘cat’ and addressing voice to it (Qin and Suzuki 2016).

Fig. 6 'Rice plant' in Sino-Tibetan.

Fig. 7 'Rice plant' in Sino-Tibetan (ST borderland enlarged).

Although rice is cultivated in the ST-speaking region, some languages are also spoken in non-rice-cultivating areas, such as the Tibetan Plateau. Therefore, mismatches between roots and meanings beyond languages can occur due to different processes of lexical diffusion.⁷ This also suggests that crop terms at the ST proto-language level have not yet been fixed for specific plants. This further implies that rice began to be cultivated after the split of ST into SN and TB, based solely on linguistic evidence.

5. 'Wheat'

Figures 8 and 9 show the word forms for 'wheat' in ST.

⁷ See, for example, Suzuki and Sonam Wangmo (2016) for the expansion of the word form *'bras* in the Tibetosphere.

- | | |
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| <p>A. stem (+ suffix) type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A-1 <i>mai</i> 麦 (monosyllabic) • A-2 <i>maizi</i> 麦子 <p>B. modifier type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> △ B-1 <i>xiaomai</i> 小麦 <p>SN</p> <p>A. PTB *m-grwa</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ A1: ⁿqo, ⁿqu, etc. ○ A2: ^{ʈo}, ^{kro}, ^{co}, ^{teo}, ^{cço}, ^{tʂʰo}¹², etc. ⊕ A3: ^{rgak}, ^{rgo}⁶, ^{lgap}, ^{ka lie}, etc. ● A4: ^{lu}, ^{ʔzi}, ^{ji}, ^{jɔ}, etc. ● A5: ^{kaj}, ^{qo}²⁴, ^{ʋiə}²⁴¹, etc. ● A6: ^{gom}, ^{goŋ}, etc. <p>B. Coronal initial type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▭ B1: ^{zi}³³, ^{zɿ}³³ ^{ze}³¹, ⁿdza, ^{tso}:^{dza}, etc. ▭ B2: ^{sa}⁶, ^{fua}⁴⁴, ^{ʂa}⁴⁴, ^{xa}³³, etc. <p>TB</p> <p>C. /m/-initial type</p> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> △ B-2 <i>ximai</i> 细麦 △ B-3 <i>hemai</i> 禾麦 △ B-4 <i>mianmai</i> 面麦 ▽ B-5 others: <i>huangmai</i> 黄麦, etc. — C. others: <i>xialiang</i> 夏粮, <i>suozi</i> 梭子 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☆ C1: <i>mu</i>, etc. ● C2: <i>se mu</i>, etc. <p>D. Semantic change type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▽ D1: ^{nē}·, ^{nje}·, ^{ne}·, etc. △ D2: ^{sʰo} wa ∕ D3: ^ʂŋo, ^ŋo ∖ D4: ^{kə} rə, ^{ka} rə, ^{kā}, ^{kar} <p>E. Loanword type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✂ E1: Sinitic; <i>maizi</i>, <i>xiaomai</i>, <i>mu tsi</i> ✂ E2: Indic; <i>ʃōu</i>, <i>joun</i>^M, <i>zong</i> — X. miscellaneous |
|--|---|

Fig. 8 'Wheat' in Sino-Tibetan.

Fig. 9 ‘Wheat’ in Sino-Tibetan (ST borderland enlarged).

The word forms for ‘wheat’ generally differ in Sinitic and TB. A small number of TB varieties spoken in Sichuan and Yunnan present forms similar to their Sinitic counterparts (Types A and B for SN and Type C for TB). This similarity does not exhibit a clear relationship with proto-level forms but with a loan process in an earlier period since wheat was introduced in China around 2600 BCE (Long et al. 2018), corresponding to the period after the split into SN and TB. Although there are some lexical similarities between languages spoken in the Sinitic-TB borderland, this is predominantly due to recent lexical borrowing.

Bradley (2011:140) proposes three TB etyma: *ša³, WrT *gro*, and *gom/goŋ. Our analysis identified two main types: A (*m-grwa group) and B (*ša³ group; south-eastern TB area). Type C is mainly attested within Type B territory. We relate Type C to the

Sinitic word *mai* (OC *m-rʰək). Bradley (2011:136) states that the Sinitic form *mai* ‘appears to be a loan from Indo-European, possibly via Turkic’. Hence, if our analysis is correct, the varieties using Type C received the Sinitic lexical form after Sinitic was borrowed from IE via Turkic (i.e., via the present Xinjiang).

The Tibeto-Burman analysis does not distinguish between Sinitic loan forms (Type E1). However, the analysis of Sinitic distinguishes *maizi* 麦子 (Type A2) from *xiaomai* 小麦 (Type B1). Type B1 was observed at several locations in Sichuan, whereas Type A2 was observed in Yunnan. In Tibeto-Burman, many loanword forms are Type A2 (Hani, Jino, Lahu, and Kucong), with a minority of Type B1 (Hani). Because Type B1 is used in the northern and central regions of the Sinitic distribution area, the use of Type B1 in TB could be a recent loan through the expansion of Putonghua.

In the Tibetosphere, the distribution of Type A2 is wide, and its form corresponds to the LT *gro*. However, in the area where the wheat grows instead of the highland barley (Yunnan), the word form for ‘wheat’ is substituted by other crops’ terms, as shown in Types D1 (< LT *nas* ‘highland barley’) and D2 (< LT *so ba* ‘barley’). It appears in the Tibetic languages, particularly in varieties spoken at lower altitudes. Therefore, vegetal cultivation is likely to trigger semantic changes. Potentially, the lexical classification of crop species in Tibetic may have originated from varieties spoken at higher altitudes.

6. Concluding words

This article examined the lexical forms for ‘dog’, ‘pig’, ‘rice plant’, and ‘wheat’ in ST languages. The SN and TB datasets were initially compiled and analysed separately following the projects *Studies of Asian Geolinguistics* and *Studies of Asian and African Geolinguistics*. This article discusses how similarities and differences appear in these words.

The lexical variation between the SN and TB was relatively large, even for basic words. Among them, ‘dog’ and ‘rice’ exhibit the lexical relationship at the root level, whereas ‘pig’ demonstrates different roots in the two language groups, and ‘wheat’ exhibits their loan relationship. Furthermore, more roots were used differently in TB than in SN.

Early loan forms and their expansion could make the two branches divergent. More case studies are needed to analyse mutual lexical development. Additionally, semantic changes are worth considering in the field of geolinguistics.

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Publication history

Date received: 21 August 2023